

21st Century Competencies needed of Librarians to Deploy and Manage Technological Tools in the Federal University Libraries of South-South Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the competencies required of librarians to deploy and manage technological tools in federal university libraries of south-south Nigeria. Three research objectives were formulated to guide the study. E-learning theory formed the basis for the theoretical framework. The study adopted a descriptive survey design; the population of the study consisted of all the hundred (100) professional librarians in the six federal university libraries in the south-south zone of Nigeria. Four-point Likert scale type of questionnaire tagged: Competency of Librarians to Deploy and Manage Technological Tools (CLDMTT) was designed and divided into Section A: Biodata, Section B: Technological Tools Deployed and Managed, Section C: Competencies of the Librarians, Section D: Challenges Associated with the Deployment. The data collected was analysed in tables, using simple percentages and mean. All analyses were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 while results were presented in tables. The findings revealed that electronic classrooms, computer workstation clusters, flexible seating areas, and wireless networks are the technological tools deployed and managed; respondents had a high level of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence, among other findings. The study recommended that extra-budgetary allocations should be made for upgrading existing technological tools or replacement with newer technologies.

Keywords: Technological Tools, Libraries, Competency, Librarians, University

Introduction

The proliferation of information and communication technologies in every sphere of society today has continually affected and redefined the competencies required to function within the work and social space. The educational sector, particularly in the ivory towers. With members of faculty consistently seeking engaging teaching methods, which of course requires support from libraries. A major component of the support structure in our tertiary institutions are faculty/lecture theatres, laboratories and libraries (Bibrowek, 2014). Of these support structure, the library plays a unique function, due to its holdings which are well organized for maximum exploitation by users. The effectiveness of a library as an instrument of education is determined by the success with which it is able to provide the user with the information he/she seeks. The library can fulfil this function best by pursuing a policy of constant self-evaluation in order to be alert to the changing needs of its users. It is perhaps, in consideration of the role of the libraries that universities pay special attention to building and equipping them.

University libraries objectives from their formation are embedded in that of the parent institution. Changes are commonplace in response to changes in the learning environment and changes in the behaviour of their libraries. The changes come in a variety of ways, from technology to personnel. Librarians are adding new, digital resources and services while maintaining most of the old, traditional resources and services. Library administrators are expected to respond to the changing needs and expectations of users and in some cases are presumed to account for their expenditures and demonstrate the outcomes they achieve. The current role of the library is to satisfy a need for an environment that cultivates students' collaboration and peer learning. The traditional role of the library was to symbolically reinforce the spirit of learning by providing areas for reading.

Libraries in playing their supportive role to the university education, provide necessary resources and services. The resources help libraries to meet the needs of their teaming patrons. Such resources range from print to non-print and electronic materials. Yusuf and Iwu (2010) asserted that different users of university libraries utilize different materials provided by these libraries; such materials as reference materials, textbooks, journals, newspapers, past projects, electronic journals etc. Also, resources like "books, journals, newspapers, government publications, indexes and abstracts as common information materials are provided and utilized by university libraries" (Nwezeh and Shabi, 2011). The traditional role of the library had been to provide trustworthy information and to help students distinguish reliable information services (Cambell, 2016). Information today in any format, can be accessed anywhere and anytime on campus (Scott, 2001). As libraries modernize, they face an increasingly harsh budget environment. The political, social and technological environment is one of transformation and uncertainty. To address this paradigm shift, libraries have been forced to implement extensive physical creations. These creations are additions to the libraries designed to address the decline of user statistics brought about by the repaid expansion and explosion of Information and the Internet.

Statement of the Problem

Technological tools have proven to be helpful in achieving library goals. They promote success in students' learning as their main goal is to provide a range of services in a convenient location where students gather to work. A decline in the usage of library services at the university level suggests that students are looking elsewhere for information resources. The libraries are losing clientele; students may visit the library to study, to socialize, to hit the newly installed café designed to lure them in, but they are not using library materials or library services like they once did ten years ago. The researcher observed that library users in the study area seemed to prefer going elsewhere for their information needs due to the explosion of information and the use of the Internet. In contemporary society, personal computers and sophisticated cell phones have become mobile libraries as they can store voluminous information which can also be easily accessed and shared. This reality has challenged conventional libraries to adopt a fresh approach by including e-library as part of their services. Also problematic is the scanty literature focusing on this area within South-South Nigeria. In more advanced countries like the United States of America,

and Canada among others, such studies abound but the same cannot be said of Nigeria in general and South-South in particular. This observed gap in the literature and the declining interest in libraries constitute the problem of this study.

Research Questions

In order to carry out an investigation into the research problem, the following research questions were drawn to serve as guide to collect relevant data:

1. What are the technological tools deployed and managed in state university libraries in South-South Nigeria?
2. What are the competencies of the librarians and other personnel involved in the deployment and management of technological tools in state university libraries in South-South Nigeria?
3. What are the challenges associated with the deployment and management of technological tools in state university libraries in South-South Nigeria?

Theoretical framework of the study

The study is based on the E-learning theory proposed by Aparicio, Bacao and Oliveira (2016). The e-learning theoretical framework of the trio contains the three main components of information systems. These components, according to Aparicio et al (2016), are people, technologies, and services. The trio argued that people interact with e-learning systems while E-learning technologies aid the direct or indirect interaction of different groups of users. On the other hand, technologies give support to incorporate content, ensure communication, and provide collaboration tools. A holistic examination of the e-learning theoretical framework showed that the e-learning stakeholders (people) are made up of customers (e.g. students, employees), suppliers (e.g. teachers, content providers and accreditation bodies) professional associations (e.g. students commissions and board of shareholders (e.g. education ministry, industry). The second dimension which e-learning technologies is made up of contents (e.g. documents, digital audio and video, authoring tools, visualization tools, knowledge repositories, journal/newsletter, learner web, post area, weblink manager, audio and video capturing, edutainment content, search engine, learner online, glossary and assessment), communication (e.g. discussion area, chat, forum, social network, email, synchronous communication) and collaboration (e.g. multi-user dialogue, sharing tool, ask an expert area, problem/solution area and one-on-one monitoring).

The last dimension which is e-learning activities have a pedagogical model (e.g. open learning, distribution learning, learning communities, communities of practice and knowledge-building communities). Finally, the theory has what the trio called instructional strategies which include contextualizing instruction, presenting and curating content, activating learning processes, assessing learner outcomes, synthesizing and sequencing processes into instructional lessons, promoting or supporting authentic learning activities, facilitating problem-solving, promoting collaboration, supporting

role-playing, supporting multiple perspectives, modelling and explaining scaffolding. This theory is relevant to the current study because it offers explanation for understanding the creation and utilization of learning commons for user satisfaction. The theory covers all aspects of the study such as the technology, the user and the contents.

Literature Review

A Library Staff qualified to deploy and manage technological tools must be responsive to the needs of users, think critically and be organized as well as organize or coordinate projects and services for the user. The librarian must be aware of current trends and have a wide base of knowledge. They must also keep tabs on the new types of library services. They must effectively evaluate the sources that they come into contact with so as to provide the user with the best information possible. They must also be able to collaborate with others to improve services and implement new services, in the profession and also with the user. The librarian must also be an advocate for the library and be involved in any outreach programs and actively promote the library and its services.

In the United States, Chisenga (2014) observed that those who staff information technology desks are usually required to have an accredited Master's degree in Library Science from the American Library Association. However, if there is a lack of qualified applicants, particularly in rural areas of the country, a person with an Associate Degree, a Certificate in Library Technology, or a Bachelor's Degree in Library Science may be performing these duties. In many university libraries, student assistants are used as the primary contact, sometimes at an "information desk". The functions of librarians according to Frank (2015) are to provide support for academic success for faculty and students through information/reference service, information literacy, consolidated assistive technology for students with disabilities, technological support, and production support. To do all these, the librarian must be familiar with Librarianship and Information Technology.

A great number of university libraries are challenged highly by a lack of quality staff. Ogbonna, (2009) opined that staffing is one of the problems facing private university libraries in Nigeria. This, believably, is not so different from even federal and state-owned universities, polytechnics and colleges of education in the country. The efficiency of the staff is very important because it can create efficient facilities which can lead to effective use of the library, and propagate and broadcast the existence of a facility. The problem according to Hillman (2014) is that the majority of librarians are trained in the traditional methods of librarianship. This means that the majority of learning commons librarians have little or no skill at all to handle the problems of readers electronically. This is a problem that needs to be tackled to help the users to utilize the available resources and services effectively.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Singh (2016) defined descriptive survey design as a "method of investigation which attempts to describe and interpret what exists at present in the form of

conditions, processes, trends, effects attitudes, beliefs etc.” it is concerned with the phenomena that are typical of the normal conditions. The target population consisted of all the one hundred (100) professional librarians in the six federal university libraries in the south-south geo-political zone in Nigeria. After a preliminary visit to the universities under study, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State established in 2011 had 11 professional librarians; Federal University of Petroleum Resources Effurun, Delta State also established in 2011 had a total of 11 professional librarians; the University of Benin, Edo state established in 1970 had 14 professional librarians. Furthermore, the University of Calabar, Cross River State being a second-generation university had 15 professional librarians; the University of Port Harcourt on the other hand established in 1976 had 22 professional librarians. Lastly, the University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State established in 1988 had 27 professionals. The entire population of 100 professional librarians was used for the study, thus there was no sampling.

Four-point Likert scale type of questionnaire tagged: Competency of Librarians to Deploy and Manage Technological Tools (CLDMTT) was designed and divided into Section A: Biodata of respondents, Section B: Technological Tools Deployed and Managed, Section C: Competencies of the Librarians, Section D: Challenges Associated with the Deployment. The instrument contained 33 items. The administration of the questionnaire was carried out by the researchers and assisted by research assistants. The data that were collected for this research were analysed in tables, using simple percentages and mean. All analyses were done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 while results were presented in tables.

Data Analysis and Interpretation of Results

The return rate of this study showed that out of the 100 copies of the questionnaire that were administered to librarians, 92 copies were filled and returned. This represents a return rate of 92%.

Research Question 2: What are the technological tools deployed and managed in Federal University libraries in South-South Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on Technological Tools Deployed and Managed in University Libraries

SN	Technological Tools Deployed	Status of the respondents				Overall		R	D
		Librarian		Users		Mean	SD		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
1	Electronic Classrooms	2.93	.95	3.08	.98	3.07	.97	1 st	HC
2	Collaborative study spaces (wired with options for data display, whiteboard, to seat at least six with varying sizes)	2.85	1.16	2.88	1.15	2.88	1.15	2 nd	HC
3	Special Reader Services	2.85	1.13	2.83	1.12	2.83	1.12	3 rd	HC
4	Spaces for meetings	2.57	1.10	2.84	1.13	2.82	1.13	4 th	HC
5	Video / DVD Access (Accommodates individual and group viewing)	2.86	1.07	2.81	1.07	2.81	1.07	5 th	HC
6	Wireless Network	2.98	1.11	2.77	1.20	2.78	1.19	6 th	HC
7	Flexible seating areas	2.66	1.14	2.75	1.20	2.74	1.19	7 th	HC
8	Circulation/Reference/Technology Help area	2.82	1.15	2.72	1.12	2.72	1.12	8 th	HC

9	Writing Centre and other academic support units and Presentation support centres	2.59	1.22	2.72	1.14	2.72	1.14	8th	HC
10	Reading area(s)	2.74	.96	2.64	1.07	2.64	1.07	10th	HC
11	Learning Commons Coordinator	3.04	1.07	2.61	1.15	2.64	1.15	10th	HC
12	OPACs (Online Public Access Catalogues)	2.81	1.02	2.62	1.13	2.63	1.12	12th	HC
13	Printing / Transfer of files / Scanning	2.74	1.11	2.52	1.14	2.54	1.14	13th	HC
Grand Mean						2.75	.59		HC

Key: R= Remarks and D = Decision

Using the principle of the real limit of numbers, the overall mean results reveal that all the thirteen variables listed in the table are highly deployed and managed in university libraries in south-south Nigeria. It should be noted that the items were re-arranged in order of mean rating for ease of understanding. Also, the overall mean showed that Electronic Classrooms and Computer workstations clusters (mean = 3.07) ranked highest while Printing / Transfer of files/ Scanning (Mean = 2.54) ranked lowest as regards technological tools deployed and managed in university libraries in south-south Nigeria

Research Question 2: What is the level of competence of librarians in deploying and managing technological tools?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on Competence of Librarians in Deploying and Managing Technological Tools in University Libraries

SN	Competence of Librarians in deploying and managing technological tools	Overall		
		Librarian Mean	SD	R
1	Information Technology Skills	2.68	1.17	HL
a	Installing printer scanner and computer systems	2.67	.92	HL
b	Computer programming	2.49	1.17	LL
c	Emailing	2.61	1.16	HL
d	Microsoft offices	2.74	1.10	HL
e	Instant Messaging technology (IM)	2.61	1.13	HL
f	Troubleshooting technology	2.91	1.08	HL
Grand Mean		2.67	.43	HL

The results of data analysis in Table 3 show all but one item was rated as high-level competence in of librarians in deploying and managing technological tools. This is because items had mean scores that range from 3.0-2.50. The respondents, however, rated computer programming competence as low level. This suggests that librarians may face a fundamental problem because they lack competence in programming. The respondents ranked higher in troubleshooting (Mean= 2.91).

Research Question 3: What is your level of agreement on these problems associated with the creation and utilization of learning commons?

Table 3: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Problems Associated with deployment and management of technological tools in the university libraries

SN	Problems	Status of the respondents				Overall		R	D
		Librarian		Users		Mean	SD		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
1	Incompetence of library staff	3.27	.97	3.18	.91	3.23	1.01	1 st	A
2	Lack of computers and accessories	3.21	.97	2.80	1.11	3.01	.97	2 nd	A
3	Poor library education	3.01	1.03	2.99	.99	3.00	.86	3 rd	A
4	Materials are not current	2.97	.99	2.97	.94	2.97	.82	4 th	A
5	The Stringent Library Rules	2.94	1.02	2.93	.98	2.93	.89	5 th	A
6	Insufficient time (opening and closing hours)	2.84	.96	2.99	.94	2.92	.83	6 th	A
7	Poor Architectural Design of the Library	2.73	.96	3.08	.89	2.90	.97	7 th	A
8	Poor Cooling/Heating system in the Library	2.80	.94	2.95	.98	2.88	.81	8 th	A
9	Limited Study Space for all Users	2.63	.91	3.02	.90	2.83	.84	9 th	A
10	Library materials are wrongly shelved	2.49	.99	3.01	1.01	2.75	.82	10 th	A
11	Poor Furniture Arrangement	2.67	.96	2.82	1.07	2.75	.83	11 th	A
12	Library staff are inexperienced	2.86	1.14	2.57	1.14	2.72	.82	12 th	A
13	Non-existence of internet connectivity in the library	2.73	1.11	2.70	1.10	2.71	.97	13 th	A
Cluster Mean						2.92	.44		A

The data presented in Table 3 revealed the mean ratings of the responses of the respondents on the problems associated with the deployment and management of technological tools. Using the criterion mean of 2.50, the table indicates that items 1-13 were above the cut-off point of 2.50 on a 4-point rating scale, this shows that the respondents agreed with these items. The standard deviation values for the seven evaluation activities ranged from 0.97 to 1.01 which implied that the respondents were not far from one another in their responses and that their responses were not far from the mean.

Looking at the two categories of respondents in the study, the results indicated that librarians and Users identified the incompetence of library staff (mean= 3.27) as a critical problem associated with the deployment and management of technological tools in university libraries in south-south

Furthermore, an indication from the grand mean (mean=2.92) showed that all the items are problems associated with the deployment and management of technological tools in Federal University libraries in the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria.

Summary of Major Findings

The result of this study showed as follows:

- Electronic Classrooms, Computer Workstations clusters, flexible seating areas, wireless networks etc. are the technological tools deployed and managed in the federal university libraries in the south-south geopolitical zone of Nigeria.
- Respondents reported a high level of competence in ICTs.

- Respondents identified incompetence of library staff and information skills respectively as a critical problem associated with the use of learning commons in university libraries in the South-South.

Discussion of Findings

Technological tools deployed and managed in state university libraries in South-South Nigeria

The results of the study indicate that technological tools deployed and managed in state university libraries in South-South Nigeria include electronic classrooms and computer workstations clusters, collaborative study spaces, adaptive Technology Lab/Special Reader Services, spaces, video/DVD Access, Wireless Networks, flexible seating areas and Equitable Access, Circulation/Reference Technology, writing Centre, Learning Commons Coordinator and an Advisory Group, OPACs and Printing/Transfer of files/Scanning. The finding of the study is consistent with that of Lippincott (2006). The author states that the technological tools have been successful in terms of getting students into the library. The use of technological tools addresses the needs of students by bringing together content and services in a physical space that is different from that of a traditional library. Technological tools typically have computers, extensive software packages, and multimedia production and editing capabilities (Lippincott, 2006).

Competencies of the librarians and other personnel involved in the deployment and management of technological tools in Federal University libraries in South-South Nigeria

The findings on competencies of librarians in the deployment and management of technological tools in state university libraries in south- south as presented indicates that among the four mentioned technological skills, the librarians had the highest competency in Information Technology Skills, and librarianship skills, Also, it is interesting to note that, in a combination of various skills, the respondents have an overall high level of competency in all the skills.

University libraries are at a crossroads in recent times. While there is a growing perception that the physical library is no longer essential to the educational experience since students increasingly rely on technology for learning and communication (Gardner and Eng, 2015) The competence of librarians is a very essential requirement for the deployment of technological tools (Lawal, 2007).

Challenges associated with the deployment and management of technological tools in Federal University libraries in South-South Nigeria

The findings of this study on research question three revealed that the problems of deployment and management of technological tools in Federal University libraries in South-South Nigeria include: poor/non-existence of internet connectivity in the library, lack of computers and accessories, poor library education, materials are not current, the stringent library rules, insufficient time, poor architectural design of the library, poor cooling/heating system in the library, limited study space for all users, poor furniture arrangement, library staff are inexperienced and incompetent. The finding of this study is consistent with

that of Ranganathan (1999) who observed passionately that “there are some staff that cannot get out of the habit of looking upon users as a nuisance. This is a problem because rather than the users being encouraged to utilize the services they are discouraged.

Lack of competence by librarians to promote users to exploit the library is a clog in the wheel of library usage. It is imperative that those who serve the users should have a reasonable level of knowledge and skills to be effective in reading services in these days that services are electronic. But the problem according to Hillman (2014) is that the majority of librarians are trained in the traditional methods of librarianship. This means that the majority of librarians have little or no skill at all to handle the problems of readers electronically. This is a problem that needs to be tackled to help the users to utilize the available resources and services effectively. There is a growing perception that the physical library is no longer essential to the educational experience since students increasingly rely on technology for learning and communication (Gardner and Eng, 2015). For most students, the library has become a virtual destination (Kamba, 2011). The Gardner and Eng (2015) study found that “73 per cent of the respondents were more likely to conduct research by using the Internet than by going to the library”. The furniture arrangement and seating capacity contribute enormously to the utilization of the resources and the services the university libraries provide. However, many libraries have large registered readers but very few and not too comfortable seats poorly arranged within a tight reading space (Okiy, 2015). The cost of new equipment can be substantial, and legacy spaces may be difficult or costly to reconfigure. In fact, designing, building, and maintaining a library common may be too big a project for a single organization or department and might require a collaborative effort among several campus entities. Another often-encountered problem is that of choosing the right services to offer in a new library common.

The challenge of technology is an expensive one. The digital natives now served in schools expect the newest equipment and software. Easy access and mobility are major concerns for students to be able to move throughout the zones according to use for the moment. Laptops and tablets maximize movement and require little space

Conclusion

Technology as it evolves will continue to influence our day to day activities, and this means that the changes must be proactively matched by libraries. Library management and university authorities must acknowledge the influence of technology, especially information and communication technologies, and actively seek opportunities to leverage these technologies to enhance teaching, learning and research. Based on the findings, the study concluded Electronic Classrooms and Computer Workstations clusters ranked highest in the respondents’ mean rating of technological tools deployed. It is also the conclusion of this study that respondents reported high competence in ICTs as technological skills. It is also the conclusion of the researcher that incompetence of library staff as a critical problem associated with use of the deployment of technological tools in university libraries in South-South, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made to the relevant authorities to improve the deployment of technological tools in university libraries:

1. Advanced computer training programme be introduced for library personnel since deployment of technological tools involved utilization of modern information resources like electronic classroom and other modern facilities. This will enable the librarian work efficiently
2. Qualified library staff should be employed to provide in-house training for other staff. this will in turn facilitate the deployment of technological tools in the library
3. As new technologies continue to be invented, extra budgetary allocations should be made for upgrading of existing technological tools or total replacement with newer technologies

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